

JAVASCRIPT DA SHARTLAR (IF, ELSEIF). JAVA SCRIPTDA SIKLLAR (WHILE, FOR, DO WHILE)

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Anotatsiya: JavaScript da shartlar (if, elseif) va sikllar (while, for, do while) - bu kodni bajarish va takrorlash uchun ishlatiladigan usullardir. Shartlar if, elseif va else kalit so'zlaridan foydalanadi va shartlarni jingalak qavs ichida yozadi. Sikllar while, for va do while kalit so'zlaridan foydalanadi va shartlarni jingalak qavs ichida yozadi. Shartlar va sikllar kodni boshqarish va optimallashtirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: if, elseif, else, while, for, do while

JavaScript da shartlar (if, elseif) - bu kodni bajarishga qaror qilish uchun ishlatiladigan usuldir. Shartlar kodni bajarishga qaror qilish uchun bir yoki bir nechta shartlarni tekshiradi va ularning natijasiga ko'ra kod bloklarini bajaradi. Shartlar if, elseif va else kalit so'zlaridan foydalanadi.

if sharti - bu eng oddiy shart turi. U bir shartni tekshiradi va agar shart rost bo'lsa, kod blokini bajaradi. Agar shart yolg'on bo'lsa, kod blokini o'tkazib yuboradi. Kod bloki faqatgina bir qator bo'lishi mumkin yoki jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi mumkin. Shart ham jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi kerak.

elseif sharti - bu avvalgi if sharti yolg'on bo'lganida ishlatiladigan qo'shimcha shart turi. U boshqa bir shartni tekshiradi va agar shart rost bo'lsa, kod blokini bajaradi. Agar shart yolg'on bo'lsa, kod blokini o'tkazib yuboradi. Kod bloki faqatgina bir qator bo'lishi mumkin yoki jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi mumkin. Shart ham jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi kerak.

else sharti - bu avvalgi barcha if va elseif shartlari yolg'on bo'lganida ishlatiladigan oxirgi shart turi. U hech qanday shartni tekshirmaydi, faqatgina kod blokini bajaradi. Kod bloki faqatgina bir qator bo'lishi mumkin yoki jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi mumkin.

Masalan:

```
var x = 10;
if (x > 0) {
  // agar x musbat son bo'lsa, quyidagi kodni bajar
  console.log("x musbat son");
} elseif (x < 0) {
  // agar x manfiy son bo'lsa, quyidagi kodni bajar
  console.log("x manfiy son");
} else {
  // agar x nolga teng bo'lsa, quyidagi kodni bajar
  console.log("x nolga teng");
}
```

JavaScript da sikllar (while, for, do while) - bu kodni bir necha marta takrorlash uchun ishlatiladigan usuldir. Sikllar kodni takrorlashga qaror qilish uchun bir yoki bir nechta shartlarni tekshiradi va ularning natijasiga ko'ra kod bloklarini takrorlaydi. Sikllar while, for va do while kalit so'zlaridan foydalanadi.

while sikli - bu eng oddiy sikl turi. U bir shartni tekshiradi va agar shart rost bo'lsa, kod blokini takrorlaydi. Agar shart yolg'on bo'lsa, sikldan chiqadi. Kod bloki faqatgina bir qator bo'lishi mumkin yoki jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi mumkin. Shart ham jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi kerak.

for sikli - bu eng keng tarqalgan sikl turi. U boshlang'ich qiymat, shart va o'sish amalidan iborat bo'lgan bir parametr qabul qiladi va parametr qiymati shartga mos kelgan davomida kod blokini takrorlaydi. Agar parametr qiymati shartga mos kelmagan bo'lsa, sikldan chiqadi. Kod bloki faqatgina bir qator bo'lishi mumkin yoki jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi mumkin. Parametr ham jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi kerak.

do while sikli - bu eng kam ishlatiladigan sikl turi. U avval kod blokini bajaradi va keyin bir shartni tekshiradi. Agar shart rost bo'lsa, kod blokini takrorlaydi. Agar shart yolg'on bo'lsa, sikldan chiqadi. Kod bloki faqatgina bir qator bo'lishi mumkin yoki jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi mumkin. Shart ham jingalak qavs ichida yozilishi kerak.

Masalan:

```
var i = 1;
while (i <= 10) {
    // agar i 10 dan kichik yoki teng bo'lsa, quyidagi kodni takrorla
    console.log(i);
    i++; // i ni 1 ga oshir
}

for (var j = 1; j <= 10; j++) {
    // j ni 1 dan boshlab 10 gacha oshirib borib, quyidagi kodni takrorla
    console.log(j);
}

var k = 1;
do {
    // quyidagi kodni avval bajar
    console.log(k);
    k++; // k ni 1 ga oshir
} while (k <= 10); // keyin k ni qiymatini tekshir
```

Xulosa

Shartlar va sikllar orasidagi farqlarni quyidagicha:

Shartlar kodni bajarishga qaror qilish uchun ishlatiladi, sikllar esa kodni takrorlash uchun ishlatiladi.

Shartlar bir yoki bir nechta shartlarni tekshiradi va ularning natijasiga ko'ra kod bloklarini bajaradi, sikllar esa bir yoki bir nechta shartlarni tekshiradi va ularning natijasiga ko'ra kod bloklarini takrorlaydi.

Shartlar if, elseif va else kalit so'zlaridan foydalanadi, sikllar esa while, for va do while kalit so'zlaridan foydalanadi.

Shartlar va sikllar nima uchun kerakligini va ularning foydalarini quyidagicha:

Shartlar va sikllar kodni boshqarish va optimallashtirish uchun kerak. Ular kodni aniqroq, tushunarliroq va qisqaroq yozishga yordam beradi.

Shartlar va sikllar kodni turli holatlarga moslashtirish va turli vazifalarni bajarish uchun kerak. Ular kodni moslashuvchan, kengaytirilgan va qayta ishlatiladigan qiladi.

Xulosa sifatida quyidagini yozishim mumkin:

Shartlar va sikllar JavaScript da kodni bajarishga qaror qilish va kodni takrorlash uchun ishlatiladigan usullardir. Ular kodni boshqarish va optimallashtirishga yordam beradi. Ular if, elseif, else, while, for va do while kalit so'zlaridan foydalanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

"JavaScript dasturlash tilida funksiyalar" avtor Rustamjon Jumayev

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